

The Embodiment of Abstract and Emotional Concepts as Product Form: The Role of Imageability and Context Availability

Deniz Leblebici-Başar * Jeanette Altarriba **

* *Istanbul Technical University
Istanbul, Turkey, denizleblebici@itu.edu.tr*
***University at Albany, State University of New York
Albany, USA, ja087@albany.edu*

Abstract: The current paper represents a portion of a design cognition study focused on the embodiment of concepts with varying emotional content (i.e., concrete, abstract and emotional) into product form. It is aimed at identifying differences in terms of cognitive processing among these three states during the initial part of the design process and during the creation of a new product. A mixed-methods approach was used including both qualitative and quantitative approaches, and retrospective protocol analysis was used as a primary source of data analysis. Professional designers were recorded and interviewed while in the process of transforming concrete, abstract, and emotional concepts, expressed via single words and various design briefs, into form, in their natural design environments. The dataset collected for the current study is analyzed in terms of imageability and context availability based on the previous research of Altarriba, Bauer and Benvenuto (1999). Results showed that imageability and context availability ratings for abstract, concrete, and emotion concepts are highly related. Preliminary findings give significant insights for understanding and describing cognitive processes engaged in by designers while embedding intangible properties into form. Results will be discussed with reference to models of cognition and design.

Key words: *Design Cognition, Design Process, Embodiment of Abstract Concepts, Imageability, Context Availability*

1. Introduction

Suh defines design as “an evolving process that can be considered as a transition from abstract concepts to concrete descriptions” [1, p25-44]. As the transition of abstract concepts into concrete forms is a difficult property to achieve for designers, it is also a challenging issue for researchers to analyze and later describe. Visualization and embodiment of emotional and abstract concepts in the mind is an important area of investigation. Van Rompay and Hekkert interpreted this challenge as lacking the ability to bridge a gap between the verbal, conceptual domain and the visual, material domain [2]. Research questions focused on “how abstract and emotional concepts were embodied as product form” give rise to another, more interesting question, that is, “what are the cognitive differences between transforming an abstract concept or a concrete concept to product form?” The present work will identify the differences related to cognitive activity in design processes across

these varying concepts. Comparisons will allow quantitative, as well as qualitative, analyses of the data. Thus, the purpose of the current work is three-fold: (1) to gain a better understanding as to how designers translate concepts that are emotional and non-emotional into product form from a cognitive perspective; (2) to compare the ways in which emotional and non-emotional concepts drive the design process specifically via the use of design briefs, oral protocols, and sketches so as to determine the similarities and differences in the ways in which designers mentally represent those concepts and translate them into form; and (3) to ultimately derive a set of “best practices” when training designers on working with concepts that vary in concreteness and emotionality, in addition to stimulating future research questions regarding cognition, emotion, and design.

2. Context Availability and Imageability Ratings for Abstract, Concrete and Emotion Words

The current research is based on the previous work of Altarriba et al. [3]. They examined the nature of emotion words in memory by comparing the ratings of the three word types (abstract, concrete, and emotion) on concreteness, imageability, and context availability scales. Their research has supplied a great amount of evidence of the distinctiveness in the cognitive processing of concrete, abstract and emotional words. According to dual coding theory [4, 5], there are two functionally independent yet interconnected representational systems: verbal and imaginal. The verbal system processes verbal information, whereas the imaginal system processes nonverbal information, typically in the form of a picture or image. These representations are differentially available in memory contingent on the concreteness of the words. Both concrete and abstract words are represented in the verbal system, but only concrete words are connected to the imaginal system. Since the image provides an additional means through which concrete words can be stored and retrieved, concrete words are more likely to be recalled better than abstract words that lack representation in the imaginal system [3].

The context availability hypothesis emphasizes the ease with which a context or circumstance can be recalled for a particular word [6, 7, 8]. The explanation states that it is easier to retrieve a context in which a concrete word appears than to retrieve a context in which an abstract word appears. For example, the context availability hypothesis would say that it is easier to think of a context for the word *chestnut* (concrete) but much more difficult to retrieve a context for the word *loyalty* (abstract). Context availability ratings are measured with a context availability scale (Figure 1). Participants are asked to rate words on whether or not they can be associated with a context or circumstance in which the word would appear. If the word can easily be associated with a certain context or circumstance, it would get a high rating. If it takes longer and is more difficult to think of a context, it would get a low rating [3].

Figure 1. Context availability scale and rating instructions [3].

Imageability can be defined as the facility to evoke a mental image by a referent. With the aid of imageability rating scales (Figure 2), words are rated on how difficult or easy it is to form an image of those words.

Figure 2. Imageability scale and rating instructions [3].

Altarriba et al.'s work indicates that there is a difference between all three word types on each of these scales. For both the context availability scale and the imageability scale, concrete words received the highest ratings, followed by emotion, and then by abstract words. As hypothesized, emotion words were rated as being easier to image and as being easier to access an appropriate context for than abstract words. Emotion words were rated lower than concrete words on the imageability and context availability scales. Although emotion words have often been included in the abstract stimuli in the literature, when rated on concreteness, imageability, and context availability they are *different* from abstract and concrete words. The results state that concepts represented by emotion words are more imageable and are easier to think of a context for than abstract words [3].

3. Experiment Overview

Design processes of varying emotional, abstract and concrete concepts were examined using a design-and-report-task which was held in six sessions of 15 minutes each. The sessions were recorded by video cameras, capturing the sketching and drawing behavior of each designer. Upon starting the sessions, the participants were informed with an informed consent form and a design brief. Each participant received three design briefs, in total—one for each of the three concepts mentioned above. Ten minutes of intervening tasks including demographic questionnaires were administered in between the design tasks. The procedure was identical processed for every participant.

3.1. Method

Participants

Twelve designers who are professionally active and contributing to the industrial design field were selected randomly. Their areas of specializations include furniture, jewelry, glassware, yachts, footwear, packaging and household appliances. Their duration of practice averaged 12 years (ranging from 2 years to 37 years). Five participants were male and seven were female with a mean age of 35 years (ranging from 25 years to 56 years). They completed the experiment individually and in their natural designing environment. The participants used their own hand designing tools. They were asked to sign an informed consent form to be videotaped and recorded during the task.

Materials

Each of the 12 participants was given an experimental session package which contained consent forms, demographic questionnaires, and three design task/report task briefs. The design task brief developed for this research was created to be appropriate for the research problem—a basic product design project focusing on the concept and appearance of the product, not too large, and feasible to complete in the available time.

Design briefs instructed the participant to design a perfume container with three different given concepts of emotional-“aggrieved”, abstract- “loyalty” and concrete- “chestnut” context. The perfume container was chosen especially for its potentially, minimal complexity in terms of overall form and form dominant structure. Thus, the

designer could work towards constructing the form without being distracted by complex aspects of product design.

Words whose meaning denoted a material object were classified as concrete words. Multidimensional scaling and factor analytic studies suggest that emotional experiences consist of both a valence (pleasant or unpleasant) and an arousal (low, medium, or high) component [9, 10, 11]. Therefore, words whose meanings were affective and had pleasantness or unpleasantness and arousal components were classified as emotion words. Words whose meanings referred to something independent from a material object that were not classified as an emotion word were designated as abstract words [12]. Referred to this data, a list of abstract, concrete, and emotion words, matched in terms of word frequency and word length, were generated and classified for further selection from the Turkish Word Frequency Dictionary database [13]. The criteria for choosing the final three words were:

- Concrete and abstract words should not contain any emotion components (i.e., neutral in terms of valence and arousal),
- Emotion words should be negatively valenced. Negative stimuli tend to capture attention and affect cognitive processing more than neutral or positive stimuli. In many situations, results for positive stimuli are equivalent to those for neutral stimuli [14].

The design briefs were formulated as shown in Figure 3. As each participant was presented with a total of three identical design briefs, one for an emotion concept, one for a concrete concept, and one for an abstract concept, the order of these briefs was counterbalanced across participants using a Latin Square Design.

<p>DESIGN BRIEF- EMOTION Design a perfume container with the given concept "AGGRIEVED". This is a form oriented design task. So it is important not to focus on design and product features (such as brand identity, intended market, dimension limitations, manufacturing processes, etc.) but to focus on the overall concept. You will have 15 minutes for completing your design sketches. You will be given one sheet A3 drawing paper and may use any of your own hand drawing tools, whatever you typically use.</p>

Figure 3. Design Task Brief for Emotion Concept.

Procedure

After consenting to participate voluntarily, the participants were given a general brief. Participants were instructed that once the study began, they would not be permitted to ask any questions of the experimenter. Before starting the design tasks, a practice task for understanding the "think aloud protocol" was held [15]. It was important to make sure that participants understood the method and what they would be doing prior to the start of the experimental tasks. Next, each participant received his/her first design brief. After reading it, this first design task was started. It was important that all the participants were given an equal amount of time, so experimenter reminded participants that they had 15 minutes for each activity. The participants were given one A3 sheet per task. The camera was set on to record starting with the first design task. After completing this task, the experimenter set turned the camera off and transferred the recording to the computer. The camera was set on again to record the corresponding report task that participants engaged in, as they viewed their performance on this particular design task. The report task began simultaneously with the screening of the participant's own designing session. In retrospective verbal reports, the participants were asked to recall the thinking process immediately after finishing the task. It is important that there is no delay between the task completion and reporting, as the working memory is accessed [15]. In the current study, we adopted Suwa and Tversky's [16] experimental procedure in order to minimize selective recall effects and simultaneously showed the participants

the videotapes of their own design sessions. The report tasks took approximately 15 minutes depending on the reporting detail of the participant. The experimenter encouraged the participant to “tell more” if needed. But the experimenter paid attention to provide an equal amount of time to maintain consistency in administration of each task, across participants. Portions of demographic questionnaires were given as intervening tasks in between the three design and report tasks. At the end of the experiment each participant was given a debriefing form, thanked, and dismissed from the session.

3.2. Results and Discussion

In this paper each participant’s protocol dataset was processed and time coded in order to draw comparisons with the theoretical motivation of attempting to understand cognitive processing differences across our three word types based on previous findings [12, 3].

Protocols consisted of two kinds of data—video recordings of the tasks and the drawings. To interpret and analyze the data, both sketches and verbal protocols (verbal and visual data) were analyzed in tandem. This procedure followed the dual mode process by Akin [17]. Both verbal and visual data were time coded and, we examined the following topics:

- amount of time spent to represent the first image to be drawn,
- amount of time spent for the first representation either visual or verbal,
- total amount spent for each design task,
- number of product alternatives produced in each design task.

Time coding was accomplished via the use of the video recordings; all sketches were numbered in the order of appearance, identifying the first image presented up to the point when the final image was formed, including the total time spent on each phase of the task as shown in the sample drawing from a participant in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sample analyses of visual material.

Mean Amount of Time to Produce a First Representation as a Drawing

As can be seen in Table 1, individuals were fastest to begin sketching for concrete concepts, followed by emotion concepts, and finally abstract concepts (see Table 1).

Table 1. The mean amount of time (in seconds) to produce the first drawing.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std Deviation	N
Abstract	98.25	89.83	12
Concrete	38.25	43.15	12
Emotional	71.41	87.66	12

The results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicate that there is a marginally significant difference between concrete, abstract, and emotion concepts in terms of the mean amount of time taken to produce a first image, $F(2, 33) = 2.27, p = .12$. The difference between abstract ($M = 98.3$) and concrete ($M = 38.3$) was significant, $t(11) = 2.10, p = .06$. No other comparisons yielded significant differences. In like with the work of Altarriba et al. [3] and Altarriba and Bauer [12] it is quite clear that concrete objects, because they naturally refer to objects that are highly imageable and can readily be placed into contexts, incite a designer to transfer concept to form much more quickly than was the case for the other two concept types. As one might expect, abstract words—words that are not typically, easily associated to an actual object and quite often to do not easily bring to mind an associate context, prompt the designer to take more time in deciding how to execute a first sketch or actual representation. While numerically, emotion concepts fall somewhere in between these two word types, they actually lie closer to abstract words, indicating that while they are often pictureable as, say, the expression of emotion on a human face, these concepts, when attempting to be translated to form, bear a closer resemblance to abstract words, in the mental representations of these word types.

Mean Amount of Time to Produce a First Representation

Table 2 shows the mean amount of time taken to produce a first representation (i.e., first verbal recall or recollection or drawing). When verbal recall is counted as a first representation, *both* the emotional concept task and the concrete concept task are first processed much more quickly than the abstract task because each of the two first tasks more easily call to mind an image as compared to the latter task (i.e., a sad human face image was recalled and announced just as fast as the chestnut image as shown in Figure 5 and 6)

Table 2. The mean amount of time (in seconds) to produce the first representation.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std Deviation	N
Abstract	62.25	66.49	12
Concrete	27.92	37.09	12
Emotional	25.08	26.96	12

The results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicate that there was a significant difference between concrete, abstract, and emotion concepts in terms of the mean amount of time taken to produce a first representation, $F(2, 33) = 4.511, p < .06$. Planned comparisons revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean time spent producing an initial response for the concrete concepts ($M = 27.92$ seconds), as compared to the abstract concepts ($M = 62.25$ seconds), $t(11) = 2.055, p = .06$. Likewise, there was a significant difference between the mean time spent producing an initial response for the emotion concepts ($M = 25.08$ seconds) as compared to the abstract concepts $t(11) = 2.396, p < .05$. As noted earlier, concrete concepts and emotion concepts tended to take about an equal amount of time to initiate response, likely due to the similarities that have been reported in the literature regarding the ease with which these concepts appear to lead to the formation of mental images (see e.g., [3]).

Figure 5. Sample sketches of the “aggrieved concept” container.

Figure 6. Sample sketches of the “chestnut concept” container.

Mean Amount of Time Spent on each Task

As can be seen in Table 3, participants finalized the concrete concept task fastest followed by the emotion concept task, and finally the abstract concept task (see Table 3). As it was easier to form an image (i.e., they already had the form of a chestnut in memory) the participants finalized the product faster in that particular task.

Table 3. The mean amount of time (in seconds) spent on each task.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std Deviation	N
Abstract	833	104.50	12
Concrete	738.58	175.14	12
Emotional	810.25	139.13	12

The results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicate that there was a significant difference between concrete, abstract, and emotion concepts in terms of the mean amount of time spent each of the three design tasks, in total, $F(2, 33) = 3.139, p = .06$. Planned comparisons revealed that there was a significant difference between the overall time spent on working with the concrete concepts ($M = 738.58$ seconds) as compared to the abstract concepts ($M = 833$ seconds), $t(11) = 2.570, p < .05$. While there was a trend towards finding a difference between the concrete concepts and the emotion concepts ($M = 810.25$ seconds), the effect was only marginally significant, $t(11) = 1.634, p = .13$. Overall, it appears that concrete concepts are somewhat easier to work with

in terms of overall time to completion, followed by emotion concepts and then, abstract concepts, respectively. Clearly, the ability to construct an image and context for concrete items lead to their ease of access and in the ability to translate that concept into form, followed by emotion concepts which in turn, have been rated higher in imageability as compared to abstract concepts (see e.g., [3]). Thus, theoretical predictions one might make about the cognitive processing of these three concepts as they are translated into form are borne out by the current set of data.

Additional Findings

The primary findings resulting from observations of the tasks, qualitative analyses and further quantitative comparisons on the data set are as follows (with quotations from designers included):

1. While working on the “chestnut” concept designers tend to draw the chestnut image right away. But while developing the form he/she tries to deny the chestnut image to create something unique. And generally, the designers weren’t satisfied with the final form they developed, thinking that they lacked the ability to come up with a creative form.

“I want to move my mind away from the real chestnut image in my mind, I start taking notes of what chestnut reminds me of; winter, fire, thorns, inner-outer, cold, paper bags...”

“...by the way I’m telling to myself that I do not want to use the image of chestnut directly...”

2. While working on the chestnut concept designers tend to consider tactile properties much more readily as texture, color, smell, etc., particularly as compared to the other two types of concepts:

“I thought of the shape and I drew. I drew something half-opened like a cross-sectional view because we always see it as it is divided and broken. These things that I drew here is to tell myself that it is a cavity ... Because of its texture, it is something that we do not want to touch; but on the other hand, I think that it is the shell of the chestnut.”

3. As the designers tried to embody a form, he/she tried to capture every single concrete visual representation of that concept that could be transferred or transformed into a 3-dimensional form. And when it is an abstract concept, it takes more time to recall and find a representative image to be embodied as a form.

“I again imagine a sphere ... as there is a container concept here spontaneously I think of voluminous forms, I mean I imagine 3-dimensional forms. It is something that you can put things in it, the natural structure of the chestnut also has this...”

4. When the concept is abstract or emotional, to access a mental image, designers tend to create metaphors, associations and context. Thus, they became more involved with the process, creating scenarios and stories. They were more satisfied with the final product in terms of creativity.

“The abstract concepts that I named as difficult was easier at this stage, supposing that it fed me more.”

5. For the “loyalty” concept, the most common association was “2 people, man and woman, 2 pieces” thus the final product was a two-pieced container in 8 out of 12 participants (67%).

“There appear two characters in front of my eyes. I cannot think of loyalty as singular. I cannot think of it as a single-sided thing either. If there is one there should be the other one, as well.”

6. For the “aggrieved” concept, the most common first representation is an unhappy face and down-necked person which led designers to try tilting the neck of their form at some time in the design process.

“In the beginning an aggrieved, unhappy person. Afterwards he/she is not really unhappy but more hesitant. Little a like hopeless. Depressed. That’s why first I thought about a sulky face, down faced, down necked...”

7. For the emotion concept, designers created more different associations, thus, the final products weren’t as similar as those that arose from the other two concepts.
8. As the emotion concept “grief” is often associated with pain, a tactile property was often used as a design measure, similar to the “chestnut” concept.

“Grief hurts you inside, aches you. Then I thought of something and started to draw. Grief may have a bitter smell but I can also create the bitter form. I saw the form and started to draw... I draw that and created a texture with small sharp triangles. It is a texture when I hold it hurts...”

4. Conclusions

The study described in this paper examined differences and similarities between cognitive processes of designers while embodying abstract, emotional and concrete verbal concepts into product form. The data set was analyzed in light of recent cognitive literature that outlines the theoretical and processing differences across these three types of concepts. Interestingly, the ways in which the concreteness or emotionality of a concept is processed in the verbal domain is directly related in the ways in which designers move from their conceptual understandings to actual forms derived from those concepts. The correspondences are many and quite often, statistically reliable (see above). Thus, one might conclude that designers first translate a verbal label into a possible pictorial image or form after considering their mental representations of those concepts, and then, with an image in mind, they begin their sketches and/or verbalizations of regarding those images. Clearly, the use of contextual memory—memory for the circumstances and settings in which those concepts were learned and/or experienced—plays a role in the development of those ideas that are then transposed into actual drawings. Knowledge generated by the current work may contribute to future research focused on generalizing these results to other types of design tasks, as well as towards the development of tools and instructional methods that might capitalize on what we know about the various characteristics of abstract, concrete, and emotional concepts in order to facilitate their embodiment or transformation into form. Likewise, measures of creativity and related skills could also be examined in terms of their impact on the ease with which images are accessed and converted into object forms leading to greater creativity in design solutions.

“There are a number of theoretically developed areas of cognitive psychology which are used to facilitate the theoretical enterprise in the design problem solving area... Conversely it would also appear that research in the area of design problem solving, because of the particular characteristics of design problems, could make a significant contribution to expanding our understanding of working memory, imagery and creative synthesis.” [18]. The current work represents a strong step towards making just such a contribution, as designers clearly performed their tasks differently depending on the concreteness, imageability, and emotional nature of the concepts they were attempting to translate into form.

6. References

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